

Probabilistic Seismic Hazard Assessment for Norway and Svalbard

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Abstract This study introduces a new probabilistic seismic hazard model for Norway and the Svalbard archipelago, incorporating recent advances in earthquake hazard assessment. Norway, on the western edge of the stable Fennoscandian shield, experiences low to moderate seismicity, with events rarely exceeding magnitude 5.5, while Svalbard has recorded moderate earthquakes near populated areas in recent years. The model is calculated using the OpenQuake Engine with input data sourced from the Norwegian National Seismic Network and supplemented with data from neighbouring countries. Compared to previous studies, the model includes five years of additional data, a lower minimum magnitude, automated quality assurance, and harmonization with neighbouring regions. Both smoothed seismicity and traditional zonation approaches are considered, and ground motion models are validated against local records. The results include hazard maps for 475- and 2500-year return period ($VS30=800$ and $VS30=3000$), peak ground acceleration estimates and hazard curves for selected sites. Results are compared with ESHM20 and other regional models. All data, configurations, and workflows are openly published, providing an updated and transparent seismic hazard assessment for Norway and Svalbard.

Non-technical summary This study provides an assessment of earthquake hazard for Norway and the Svalbard archipelago, estimating the potential for future earthquake shaking. Although Norway lies within a stable geological region and generally experiences small earthquakes, occasional moderate events can occur. At Svalbard, we have seen moderately sized earthquakes near populated areas in recent years. To estimate the hazard, we applied state-of-the-art methods and used the latest data from the Norwegian National Seismic Network and neighbouring countries. Compared to previous studies, this new model includes five additional years of observations, improved data quality validation, and better alignment with surrounding regions. The results include maps showing expected ground shaking across the study area (with return periods of 475 and 2500 years), as well as hazard curves and disaggregation plots for selected locations to identify the

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25 earthquake scenarios that contribute most to the hazard. These findings are compared with Eu-
26 ropean and regional models to validate consistency. All data and workflows are openly available,
27 providing a transparent and up-to-date earthquake hazard assessment for Norway and Svalbard.

28

29 Graphical summary

1 Introduction

Norway, located on the western edge of the stable cratonic Fennoscandian shield, experiences low to moderate seismicity (Gregersen et al., 2021). The seismic hazard in Norway is generally low with historical events up to magnitude MW 5.9 (Mäntyniemi et al., 2020). Previous seismic hazard studies have found the highest hazard along the western coast of Norway, with PGA values in the range 0.05 - 0.1 g for a return period of 475 years (Danciu et al., 2021; Lindholm et al., 2025).

The Norwegian archipelago Svalbard, located in the Arctic, at 74 to 81°N directly north of Norway, also shows a low to moderate level of seismicity varying across the region. A total of 13 events of MW 5.5 and above have been recorded since 1981, including one of MW 6.1 offshore in Storfjorden in 2008 (Ottemöller et al., 2013).

As communities in Norway are growing, and infrastructure is becoming more complex, the vulnerability to earthquake hazards is increasing, underlining the need for up-to-date reliable hazard estimates to evaluate the impact of the moderate level of seismicity, as well as the impact of larger events (The Norwegian Directorate for Civil Protection (DSB), 2019).

A regional seismic hazard study was recently published by (Lindholm et al., 2025). Prior to this, the most recent publicly available seismic hazard assessment for Norway dates back to 2000 (Bungum et al., 2000). Around that time, several regional and multinational models were also developed, encompassing Scandinavia, the North Sea, and broader northern Europe. These efforts significantly contributed to the foundational understanding of seismic hazard in the region (Grunthal et al., 1999; Mäntyniemi et al., 2001; Wahlstrom and Grunthal, 2001). Despite the recent publication of the 2025 study, further improvements are attainable by using a more up-to-date catalogue, incorporating recent advancements in ground motion models, and through regional harmonization of the catalogue and zonation. Furthermore, new hazard results can be made more accessible by focusing on transparency and reproducibility.

In this study, we extended the earthquake catalogue significantly and incorporated state-of-the-art methods and ground motion models that have not been considered in previous hazard models for Norway. We compiled data from several national and international earthquake catalogues covering Norway and Svalbard, including events of magnitude ≥ 1 through 2023. This comprehensive dataset offers broad temporal and magnitude coverage to reduce the epistemic uncertainty associated with low to moderate seismicity. Non-tectonic events were filtered out using statistical methods. Ground motion models based on analogous tectonic settings, calibrated against local observations, were implemented to further refine the ground motion estimates. Open-source tools with advanced processing capabilities were employed to ensure transparent, adaptable hazard calculations across a dense regional grid.

The objective of this paper is to provide a new and up-to-date open-access seismic hazard model for continental Norway and the Svalbard archipelago, based on a probabilistic framework using state-of-the-art methodology. The results of our analysis can be used to adjust the national building codes for Norway, provide a baseline hazard level for upcoming geological carbon storage ventures, and offer public and private access to a comprehensive assessment of the likelihood of future ground motion in Norway. The hazard estimates provide an accurate evaluation of the likely shaking, aiding in better preparedness and an improved understanding of the economic and societal risk earthquakes may pose.

In this paper, we begin by describing the regional seismicity and seismotectonic setting of the study area. Next, we summarize local and regional earthquake hazard assessments and review recent hazard studies from nearby regions. We then outline the methodology used, including data processing routines, development of a seismic source model, choice of ground motion model, handling of uncertainties, and the tools and software used. Finally, we present and discuss the results, including a comparison with recent hazard models.

2 Seismicity and seismotectonics

2.0.1 Continental Norway

Norway is located in northern Europe, on the western edge of the stable East European Craton, also referred to as the Fennoscandian Shield (Gee and Stephenson, 2006). It has a long coastline facing the North Sea, Norwegian Sea, and Barents Sea, with the Caledonian mountain chain forming the central structure. Off the western coast lies a passive continental margin, with the active North Atlantic mid-ocean ridge further west. A map showing the relative location and highlighting areas of interest is included in the online supplement.

On a global scale, the level of seismicity in Norway can be considered low to moderate (Gregersen et al., 2021). On average, Norway experiences a magnitude 4-5 earthquake roughly once a year, with smaller events of magnitude 3-3.5 felt regularly. As seen in Fig. 1, the seismic activity is primarily concentrated in coastal and offshore regions, with the highest occurrence rates on and offshore Western Norway, in Nordland and along the continental shelf.

Norway has a long history of reported earthquakes, with records dating back to medieval times. Significant historical onshore/nearshore events include the MW 5.9 Lurøy event in Nordland in 1819, the largest onshore/nearshore event on record (Mäntyniemi et al., 2020), the 1904 MW 5.4 Oslofjord event, and the 1759 MW 5.6 Kattegat event (Mäntyniemi et al., 2020). Further offshore, there are records of a MW 5.7 event in the Vøring Basin in 1866 and a MW 5.3 event in the Viking Graben in the northern North Sea in 1927. More recent notable events include the MW 5.3 1988 Vøring Basin event, the MW 5.2 1989 event in the northeastern North Sea just off the coast of western Norway (Hansen et al., 1989), and the 2022 MW 5.1 event, just off the coast from Florø (Jerkins et al., 2023).

Geological evidence indicates the presence of postglacial faults, such as the Stuuragurra Fault in Finnmark, which experienced major prehistoric, postglacial ruptures; fault extent and displacement support a magnitude 7+ event (EGU, 2020; Olsen and Olesen, 2023). Similar faults are found extending into northern Finland and Sweden, as well as in western Norway (Olesen et al., 2013).

2.0.2 Svalbard

The Norwegian archipelago Svalbard is located 50-200 km east of the northern part of the Mid Atlantic Ridge, in the Arctic. The archipelago is a remnant following the Caledonide Orogen, which opened the Norwegian-Greenland Sea (Gee and Teben'kov, 2004). Despite the close proximity to the spreading ridge the archipelago is still considered intraplate (Mitchell and Chan, 1978) and experiences a moderate level of seismicity (Ottemöller et al., 2021).

The highest level of seismicity in the region is observed along the spreading ridge, Fig 1. Other regions of significant earthquake activity are the greater Storfjorden area on the southeastern side of Spitsbergen, the western coast of Spitsbergen, as well as on Nordaustlandet, in the northern region of the archipelago (Fig. 1).

103 Significant events include the 1976 MB5.6 event at Heerland on the western shore of Storfjorden (Mitchell and
 104 Chan, 1978), the 2003 MW5.4 at Hopen Island, 2008 MW6.1 in Storfjorden (Pirli et al., 2010), the largest observed in
 105 Norway and part of a sequence of 16 ML+ events, and the 2016 MW5.1 at Edgeøya just south of the Svalbard peninsula
 106 (Ottemöller et al., 2021).

Figure 1 Earthquake distribution within the study areas of continental Norway (1497–2023) and Svalbard (1946–2023), magnitudes MW 2–6.2. Pink circles indicate events within the complete catalogue range; grey circles are outside. Larger events are shown with darker colours. Earthquakes with MW ≥ 5.1 (Norway) and MW ≥ 5.5 (Svalbard) are labelled with year and magnitude. Blue and black arrows show principal stress directions (Norway: Fjeldskaar et al. (2000); Svalbard: Mitchell et al. (1990); Ottemöller et al. (2021)). The black borders outline the respective study areas. Maps created in ArcGIS Pro. Background maps: ESRI.

107 2.1 Stress-generating mechanisms

108 The cause of earthquakes in Norway can be attributed to multiple stress generating mechanisms. As evident in Fig. 1,
 109 the primary source of stress in both regions is compressional forces in the form of ridge push from the North Atlantic
 110 Mid-Ocean ridge. The resulting stress depends on crustal thickness and plate rheology. The thick crustal structure
 111 of the Fennoscandian shield reduces the resulting tectonic stress, while the thinner crust in the coastal and offshore
 112 regions experience proportionally higher stress (Fejerskov and Lindholm, 2000). At Svalbard the ridge push force
 113 results in an EW stress direction (Bungum et al., 1982; Mitchell et al., 1990; Ottemöller et al., 2021).

114 Secondary sources of stress include the density contrast at the continental margin, which causes tension in the
 115 continental crust and compression in the oceanic crust, perpendicular to the margin (Fjeldskaar et al., 2000). Sedi-

ment loading also contributes, causing compression beneath the loaded region and tension in the offloaded region as sediments move from higher to lower areas. Another source of stress is the unloading due to deglaciation following the last ice age (Fejerskov and Lindholm, 2000; Olesen et al., 2013).

2.2 Seismicity by region

While Norway generally experiences low to moderate seismicity, there is considerable spatial variation in seismic activity, stress orientations, and the stress driving mechanisms. A brief regional overview is provided below. See the map highlighting areas of interest in the online supplement for reference.

2.2.1 Onshore

Southwestern and Western Norway, along with Nordland, exhibit the highest levels of onshore seismicity. Activity is primarily concentrated along the coast and is driven by a combination of ridge push and isostatic uplift. In-situ borehole measurements indicate a dominant NW–SE stress orientation (Fejerskov and Lindholm, 2000).

In Southeastern Norway, the Oslo Graben, a failed Permian rift, is characterized by a complex stress regime, thinned crust, and prominent normal faulting (Gregersen et al., 2021). Shallow earthquakes are typically associated with normal faulting, while deeper events tend to exhibit strike-slip or reverse mechanisms. Contributing stress factors include sedimentary loading and remanent stress from Permian magmatic and rifting events (Olesen et al., 2013). Historically, this region has experienced some of Norway's largest earthquakes, including the 1904 M5.4 Oslofjord event and the 1759 M5.6 Kattegat event (WOOD, 1988). However, seismicity in recent decades has been comparatively low.

Central Norway experiences limited seismic activity. The Caledonian Mountain Chain is largely aseismic, with minor activity occurring along the coast north of Trondheim. The thick crust in the region dampens the ridge push stress, and the present-day effect of isostatic uplift is limited, as maximum stress is concentrated near the former ice margin (Fejerskov and Lindholm, 2000).

Along the coast in Nordland, seismicity is clustered and predominantly shallow. This activity is largely attributed to local extensional stress in a NW–SE direction, driven by isostatic adjustment and sedimentary offloading (Shiddiqi et al., 2022). The region is also notable for the largest historical onshore earthquake in Norway, a M5.9 event in 1819 (Mäntyniemi et al., 2020), and a M5.4 earthquake that occurred just off the coast in 1894.

Finmark has a low level of instrumentally recorded seismic activity. The region, located partly on the Fennoscandian shield, is home to a significant number of post glacial faults (Olsen and Olesen, 2023). Displacement and orientation of structures in the area indicate a compressional stress regime oriented in NNW-SSE direction (Fjeldskaar et al., 2000).

2.2.2 Offshore

The southern Barents Sea is seismically relatively quiet. Seismicity generally follows the continental shelf edge and pre-existing margins. In situ measurements reveal a NNW-SSE stress direction, consistent with the ridge-push from the spreading ridge (Bungum and Lindholm, 1997).

In the Norwegian Sea, seismicity is moderate and closely follows the continental shelf. The Trøndelag platform, located between the continental shelf and central Norway, shows little to no seismic activity. The continental margin

152 here is subject to deviatoric tensional stress in the continental crust and compressional stress in the oceanic crust
153 (Olesen et al., 2013). Additionally, sediment loading along the Barents Sea margin and the Trøndelag Platform induces
154 compression beneath the load, and tension in adjacent areas (Fejerskov and Lindholm, 2000).

155 In the Lofoten Basin, located in the northwest Norwegian Sea, some of the largest offshore earthquakes on record
156 have occurred, including the 1929 M6.1 event and the 1959 M5.8 event (Byrkjeland et al., 2000). Further south, the
157 Vøring Basin experienced a M5.7 event in 1866 and another M5.3 event in 1988 (Hansen et al., 1989).

158 The northern North Sea exhibits the highest level of seismicity in Norway, with frequent magnitude 4–5 events. A
159 recent example is the MW5.1 2022 earthquake in the Tampen Spur region (Jerkins et al., 2023). Seismicity is concen-
160 trated along the coastline, the passive margin, and the Viking Graben. The dominant driving mechanism is ridge-
161 push, enhanced by sediment loading, resulting in regional NW–SE compression, as confirmed by in-situ stress mea-
162 surements (Fejerskov and Lindholm, 2000; Havskov and Bungum, 1987). The largest recorded event in the region was
163 the widely felt MW5.3 1927 earthquake in the Viking Graben (Bungum et al., 1991). In contrast, the central North Sea
164 shows lower seismicity, with most events aligned along the Central Graben. The prevailing stress direction remains
165 NW–SE (Bungum et al., 1991).

166 **2.2.3 Svalbard**

167 The majority of seismic activity in this region is concentrated on or near the Mid-Atlantic Ridge. The closest ridge
168 segment is the ultraslow-spreading Knipovich Ridge, spanning about 500km from the Mohns Ridge in the South to
169 the Molloy transform fault in the North (Meier et al., 2021). Major faults, likely formed during the Paleozoic, strikes
170 NNW-SSE through the peninsula (Chan and Mitchell, 1985).

171 In the greater Storfjorden area, earthquake activity does not align with the major fault orientations observed
172 on Spitsbergen. This region produces a high number of low-magnitude events, along with regular occurrences of
173 moderate earthquakes (Junek et al., 2013). Moment tensor inversion of the 2008 Storfjorden earthquake sequence
174 indicates SW-NE oriented extensional faulting, perpendicular to the Billefjorden Fault Zone (Junek et al., 2013; Ot-
175 temöller et al., 2021).

176 The island's recent seismicity is fairly sparse outside the greater Storfjorden area and Nordaustlandet. The pre-
177 dominant stress is the compressive stress from the ridge push, striking generally NW in combination with local
178 tectonic stress in the E-W direction (Chan and Mitchell, 1985; Junek et al., 2013).

179 The Barents Sea is far from monitoring networks, but the seismicity is believed to be low. While some larger
180 historical events have been recorded (Morozov et al., 2019), these occurred closer to the Franz Josef Islands and lie
181 outside the area of interest for this paper.

182 **2.3 Previous hazard studies**

183 The recent release of the pan-European hazard model ESHM20 (Danciu et al., 2021), which superseded the ESHM13
184 model (Woessner et al., 2015) constituted a significant advancement to the development of seismic hazard models.
185 This kicked off parallel efforts to update the national hazard assessments across Northern Europe, leading to new up-
186 to-date models for Sweden (Joshi et al., 2024), Finland (Fülöp et al., 2022), the UK (Mosca et al., 2022) and an Offshore
187 UK model covering the North Sea (Mosca et al., 2024). A new Danish model was released following ESHM13 (Voss

188 [et al., 2015](#)). Additionally, a sensitivity study for low-seismicity regions ([Fülöp et al., 2022](#)) was developed and a study
189 was conducted comparing the ESHM20 results with results obtained from the Finnish model at two Finnish nuclear
190 powerplant sites ([EGU, 2025](#)).

191 The earliest hazard assessments in the region were a hazard model for the Norwegian Continental shelf areas
192 ([Bungum and Dahle, 1989](#)) and a model for the North Sea ([Burton and Marrow, 1989](#)), as well as a Fennoscandian
193 model, released following the 1992 FENCAT release ([Mäntyniemi et al., 1993](#)). In the late 1990s, in conjunction with
194 the release of Eurocode8, several overlapping regional and multinational hazard estimates were published, including
195 a joint model for Norway, the North Sea, and the United Kingdom ([Bungum et al., 2000](#)), a model for Sweden, Finland,
196 and Denmark ([Wahlstrom and Grunthal, 2001](#)), a European model, published as part of the Global Seismic Hazard
197 Assessment Program (GSHAP) ([Grunthal et al., 1999](#)) and a hazard assessment for northern Europe ([Mäntyniemi
198 et al., 2001](#)). Following this, there were no new regional hazard assessments for Norway until the recently published
199 model by ([Lindholm et al., 2025](#)).

200 A comparison of these hazard models reveals similar regional patterns, although the reported ground motion
201 intensity levels differ. These variations can be attributed to differences in the earthquake catalogue, ground motion
202 models, or other model parameters.

203 **3 Data and methods**

204 The goal of Probabilistic Seismic Hazard Assessment (PSHA) is to estimate the probability of exceeding a given level of
205 ground motion at any location due to any feasible earthquake. This provides critical insights for engineering design
206 and societal preparedness. The framework for PSHA, originally developed by [Cornell et al. \(1968\)](#) and refined by
207 [McGuire \(1993\)](#) integrates three key components:

- 208 1. A Seismogenic Source Model, describing the rate and spatial distribution of earthquakes.
- 209 2. A Ground Motion Model (GMM), estimating the level of ground shaking from seismic events.
- 210 3. An Uncertainty Model, accounting for variability in both seismic sources and ground motion predictions.

211 Hazard calculations for Svalbard and mainland Norway were conducted separately due to lack of spatial overlap.
212 However, both assessments utilized the same workflow, software, and tools. The workflow, along with descriptions
213 of software, tools and regional adaptations, is presented in this section. The hazard calculation was conducted using
214 the Open Quake Engine ([Pagani et al., 2014](#)), and results visualized using ArcGIS Pro.

215 Two earthquake catalogues were compiled and refined to represent the seismicity in mainland Norway and Sval-
216 bard, respectively. Based on the observed seismicity, regional geology, and tectonics, we defined area source zones
217 for each region that captured the geographical distribution of seismicity, before calculating the associated occur-
218 rence rates. To complement this traditional zonation approach, a smoothed seismicity model was also developed
219 using a fixed smoothing bin size and a fixed b-value.

220 A ground motion model logic tree was assembled using models from regional studies and tectonically similar
221 regions. The development of a custom Norwegian GMM has been constrained by the limited quantity and range of
222 local strong-motion data, largely due to long source-to-station distances and low seismicity. To validate the selected
223 models, we compared the estimated acceleration with measured acceleration from a selection of recent moderate

224 events.

225 **3.1 Seismogenic Source Model**

226 **3.1.1 Earthquake Catalogue**

227 To ensure a robust, representative, and comprehensive earthquake catalogue for our regions, we used the earth-
228 quake database of the Norwegian National Seismic Network (NNSN; [Ottemöller et al. \(2018\)](#)) as the foundation and
229 supplemented it with other national and international catalogues, including data from the Geological Survey of Den-
230 mark and Greenland (GEUS; [GEUS Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland \(1976\)](#)), the Swedish National Seis-
231 mic Network (SNSN; [Lund et al. \(2021\)](#)), the British Geological Survey (BGS; [Galloway \(2016\)](#)), and the Fennoscandian
232 earthquake catalogue (FENCAT; [Uski et al. \(2025\)](#)). This approach increased the data volume, especially in the bor-
233 der regions, promoting completeness. The data was geographically confined to continental Norway and the Svalbard
234 archipelago, including a 300 km perimeter, following standard practice as presented by Baker et al., 2021. The mag-
235 nitude threshold was set at a minimum of 1, encompassing data up to and including 2023.

236 The catalogue for continental Norway included both instrumental and historical events, spanning over 500 years,
237 with the earliest reported event in 1497. This catalogue was compiled using various magnitude scales and data for-
238 mats. In contrast, the catalogue for the Svalbard archipelago contained only instrumental data, with the first event
239 recorded in 1964.

240 To maintain a representative and consistent catalogue, we employed semi-automated data harmonization and
241 quality assurance routines. Each dataset was first standardised to ensure uniform formatting and was meticulously
242 reviewed for statistical outliers in both magnitude and temporal distribution. The revised datasets were then merged
243 and again reviewed for statistical outliers as well as potential duplicates. In addition to limiting duplicate records,
244 the semi-automated workflow aimed to identify potential non-tectonic events, eliminate likely erroneous reports,
245 harmonize the magnitudes, and filter out dependent events such as aftershocks and clusters. The complete workflow
246 is illustrated in Fig. 2, with a detailed description of each step available in the Online Supplement.

247 Following the automated analysis, we manually reviewed the data to further identify any clusters or trends in the
248 catalogue that indicated a non-poissonian distribution. We also manually reviewed large-magnitude events (M4.5+)
249 to ensure consistency with magnitudes published in scientific literature and technical reports. Older historical events
250 were verified against the FENCAT catalogue ([Oinonen et al., 2024](#)) and the Scandinavian Earthquake Archive ([Dahle,
251 2025](#)). A statistical overview of the complete section of each catalogue can be seen in the online supplement.

252 Following the initial quality control, magnitudes were harmonized and converted to moment magnitude. The
253 magnitudes were converted using magnitude relations obtained through orthogonal distance regression analysis
254 ([Weatherill et al., 2016](#)) (on events with magnitudes reported for multiple agencies and/or scales. Most events in
255 the database were reported using the local magnitude (ML). A moment magnitude was only reported for a small
256 percentage of all events, making it difficult to construct robust conversion relationships. To reduce uncertainty, we
257 decided to conduct a two-step conversion following the flowchart included in the online supplement, with NNSN
258 (callsign: BER) as the primary agency and the moment magnitude (MW) as the preferred scale. The regression
259 relationships are also listed in the online supplement and were chosen based on data availability and quality of fit.

260 Dependent events, i.e., aftershocks, foreshocks and earthquake swarms, were removed to promote Poissonian

261 distribution, as the statistical tools utilized require that all data points are independent of each other. Dependent
262 events were identified and filtered based on interevent time, relative location and magnitude. The time and distance
263 limits were magnitude dependent and sourced from the SEISAN software subroutine 'ASSO' (Havskov et al., 2020).
264 The success of the declustering process was verified by plotting the inter-event time distribution, the frequency of
265 temporal gaps between successive events, as shown in the statistical overview in the online supplement. The lognor-
266 mal pattern matched expectations for a Poisson process, confirming effective declustering.

267 The final catalogue included 10610 events for continental Norway and 9062 events for Svalbard. These catalogues
268 constitute the foundation for the seismogenic source models. The geographical distribution of events can be seen
269 in Fig. 1. The magnitude distribution as a function of time, the magnitude frequency distribution and the hourly
270 distribution of the events can all be seen in the statistical overview in the online supplement. These figures are
271 consistent with a Poissonian distribution in time and space and a logarithmic distribution of magnitudes suggesting
272 tectonic origin of the final complete catalogue.

Figure 2 Workflow for the semi-automated data harmonization and quality assurance routine. Each dataset is first standardized to ensure uniform formatting, then reviewed for statistical outliers in both magnitude and temporal distribution. The revised datasets are merged and re-evaluated to identify and remove duplicates. The workflow includes magnitude harmonization and procedures to detect and exclude likely non-tectonic events, erroneous reports, and dependent events such as aftershocks and clusters. The workflow is described in detail in the Online Supplement.

273 3.1.2 Zonation

274 Due to the low to moderate levels of seismic activity and the complex fault structures and deformation zones in the
275 study area, we were unable to attribute recorded seismicity to specific fault structures. Consequently, the seismo-
276 genic source model relies on area sources to describe the seismicity in both regions. To mitigate any bias resulting
277 from source delineation, these were complemented with zonation-free models described in section 3.1.5 Smoothed
278 Seismicity Model.

279 We delineated the area sources based on the observed seismicity with $MW \geq 2.0$, considering also geological and
280 tectonic data where available. This resulted in a total of 31 source zones for continental Norway and 18 source zones

for the Svalbard archipelago (Fig. 3). This delineation was harmonised with neighbouring countries during a joint Nordic workshop in January 2023 Bergen, Norway, to ensure consistency across national borders (Fülöp et al., 2025).

Some of the delineated source zones contained too few earthquakes to reliably determine recurrence parameters. We therefore introduced large-scale zones to each represent an overall seismotectonic regime. For continental Norway this included: an offshore zone, a northern onshore zone, and a southern onshore zone (Fig. 3 left). The offshore zone encompasses the entire ocean section, excluding some near-coast regions. The northern onshore zone includes the continental and coastal regions of central and northern Norway and Sweden, excluding the coastal region to the east towards the Bothnian Bay. This delineation is justified based on the geographical extent of reported events prior to 1900, which correlates with historical population centers in the region. The southern onshore zone includes Oslo, Kattegat, southern Sweden, Jutland, and the coast along the western shore of the Bothnian Bay.

For the Svalbard archipelago, we delineated three regional zones from west to east (Fig. 3 right): the western ocean region, which includes the Knipovich Ridge, Fram Strait, and Greenland Sea; the central region, encompassing Spitsbergen, Nordaustlandet, and smaller islands, as well as near-shore regions extending into the Storfjord Bank and Storfjordrenna; and the eastern region, primarily consisting of the Arctic Ocean and Barents Sea.

Figure 3 Area, regional, and tectonic zonation for seismic hazard modelling in Norway (left) and Svalbard (right). Area source zones form the basis for recurrence estimates, supported by regional zones where data is sparse. For Norway, a tectonic zonation separates the stable cratonic region in the east from the coastal and offshore regions in the west, forming the basis for the ground motion model logic tree. Zonation is delineated from observed seismicity ($MW \geq 2$) and tectonic features from the Norwegian Petroleum Directorate. Maps created in ArcGIS with ESRI background layers.

3.1.3 Completeness

When determining earthquake activity rates, only the complete part of the catalogue is considered. An initial review revealed significant geographical variation in seismogenic history. Historically reported earthquakes correlate well with population centers at the time, meaning we have the longest temporal history in Southern Norway, Southern Sweden and along Sweden's eastern coast toward the Bothnian Bay. Northern Norway and Lapland have much shorter histories, and the offshore records are limited, except near-shore. In modern history, with the expansion and unification of the seismological network in the 1970s and 1980s (Sørensen et al., 2024), there is much better instrumental coverage, with improvements made in instrumentation, processing routines, and the number of stations.

To accommodate regional differences in recording history, we created regionally varying completeness thresholds for the following regional zones: Southern Onshore, Northern Onshore, and Offshore. The full list of completeness thresholds is given in Fig. 4. The regional zones are delineated in Fig. 3.

A notable decline in moderate-magnitude ($MW \geq 4$) events over the past five decades in continental regions coincides with the transition to digital instrumentation, suggesting a historical bias toward larger magnitudes. This may indicate that magnitudes of historical earthquakes are overestimated, but more detailed analysis is required to conclude on that matter. To address this potential bias, we developed a logic-tree catalogue with three branches:

1. Full catalogue: quality-controlled, with regionally varying completeness thresholds.
2. Time-limited: instrumentally recorded events after network expansion in 1970 for higher consistency.
3. Magnitude-limited: minimum magnitude set to 3 across all regions to reduce anthropogenic and offshore detection sensitivity effects.

This strategy supports a more reliable hazard assessment, particularly in low-seismicity regions where the trade-off between data quality and quantity is most pronounced. Either focusing on the quality of recent instrumental events, omitting potentially exaggerated historical events which could lower the true b-value, or focusing on larger events, omitting potentially non-tectonic low magnitude events which would artificially inflate the b-value. These three branches resulted in 607, 561 and 448 complete events, respectively, and given a relative weight of 0.45 for the historical and 0.15 for the two alternate branches, with the remaining 0.25 given to the smoothed seismicity branch described in section 3.1.5.

For the Svalbard dataset, we observed regional variation in detection thresholds for lower magnitude events, but no temporal variation on account of the short recording history. To accommodate the significant variance in observed seismicity, we varied the completeness using the three regional zones based on proximity to stations and relative seismicity (Fig. 3). This accounted for variations in detection capabilities, likely due to station coverage and event distance, allowing for more accurate seismicity rate estimates. This resulted in 449 complete events. The completeness thresholds for each zone are shown in Fig. 4.

3.1.4 Recurrence rates

The recurrence rates for each area zone were calculated using OpenQuake's implementation of the Weichert method (Weichert, 1980). For a selection of source zones in Western Norway (zones 6, 12 and 18), and for source zones with less than 30 events within the completeness period, the b-value was fixed to the regional b-value determined for the

COMPLETENESS BY REGION

Continental Norway Full catalogue				Continental Norway Catalogue > 1970				Continental Norway Catalogue > Magnitude 3				Svalbard Full catalogue			
Magnitude	Offshore	Onshore South	Onshore North	Magnitude	Offshore	Onshore South	Onshore North	Magnitude	Offshore	Onshore South	Onshore North	Magnitude	Barents Sea	Ridge	Spitsbergen
[2.0-2.5)			2015	[2.0-2.5)			2015	[2.0-2.5)				[2.0-2.5)			
[2.5-3.0)		2010	2010	[2.5-3.0)		2010	2010	[2.5-3.0)				[2.5-3.0)			
[3.0-3.5)	1985	2005	2005	[3.0-3.5)	1985	2005	2005	[3.0-3.5)	1985	2005	2005	[3.0-3.5)			2015
[3.5-4.0)	1980	1980	1980	[3.5-4.0)	1980	1980	1980	[3.5-4.0)	1980	1980	1980	[3.5-4.0)	1995		2012
[4.0-4.5)	1960	1970	1950	[4.0-4.5)	1970	1970	1970	[4.0-4.5)	1960	1970	1950	[4.0-4.5)	1995	2000	2000
[4.5-5.0)	1960	1920	1920	[4.5-5.0)	1970	1970	1970	[4.5-5.0)	1960	1920	1920	[4.5-5.0)	1995	2000	2000
[5.0-5.5)	1900	1885	1885	[5.0-5.5)	1970	1970	1970	[5.0-5.5)	1900	1885	1885	[5.0-5.5)	1995	1995	2000
[5.5-6.0]	1860	1750	1750	[5.5-6.0]	1970	1970	1970	[5.5-6.0]	1860	1750	1750	[5.5-6.0]		1995	2000
												[6.0-6.5)		1995	2000

Figure 4 Thresholds for catalogue selection and regional completeness zones used for Svalbard and continental Norway. Each table represents a branch with regional variation in completeness. Norway's three branches represent (1) full catalogue with region-specific completeness thresholds, (2) high-quality instrumental subset post-1970, and (3) uniform MW 3.0 threshold to limit anthropogenic and offshore effects. The regional division corresponds to the regional zonation outlined in Fig. 3.

regional zone containing the source zone in question. The a-value was then calculated from the observed data in the source zone using the fixed b-value. The associated uncertainties were adopted from the regional models. For Svalbard this event threshold was increased to 35. An exception was also made for the easternmost source zones within Swedish borders, where we judged the processing done by Joshi et al. (2024) in conjunction with the Swedish seismic hazard study to be better informed with regard to anthropogenic influence and completeness. For these regions we therefore adopted the seismicity rates reported for the comparable zone. This ensured consistent hazard levels in border regions. For consistency, the regional southern onshore zone was also confined to within Norway's borders to limit anthropogenic influence on the recurrence estimates. A full overview of the recurrence rates, and associated uncertainty, for zones for Norway and Svalbard is included in tables 1 and 2 in the online supplements.

3.1.5 Smoothed Seismicity Model

To mitigate potential biases associated with the delineation of area source zones, we implemented a smoothed seismicity model. Following the methodology of Frankel et al. (1995), we defined an equally spaced grid of point sources with a fixed spacing of 25 km. Each seismic event in the complete catalogue was mapped to the nearest grid point, resulting in a subset of events associated with each point.

Using a fixed b-value of 0.8, based on the average b-value of the event catalogue, we computed the corresponding a-value for each grid point using the OpenQuake model-building toolkit. These a-values were then spatially smoothed using a Gaussian kernel with a standard deviation of 3 and a bandwidth of 41.25 km, equivalent to 1.7 times the grid spacing. The smoothed a-values were normalized to preserve the total seismicity rate. A map overview displaying the smoothed seismicity rate at each grid point atop the earthquake catalogue can be seen in Fig. 5.

The resulting grid of smoothed and normalized a-values, combined with the fixed b-value, was used to generate a set of grid-based point sources in OpenQuake, forming the basis of the smoothed seismicity model. All other model parameters, including the ground motion models, were kept consistent with those used in the area source approach.

353 The smoothed seismicity model was incorporated into the logic tree at the same hierarchical level as the area source
 354 models with a weight of 0.25.

355 The smoothed seismicity model captures well the local seismicity variations and avoids the averaging that we see
 356 especially in low seismicity regions in the zonation-based model. However, a smoothed model may fail to capture
 357 the inherent unpredictability of stable continental regions, where moderate events can occur in areas previously
 358 considered seismically quiet (Johnston and Kanter, 1990; Wiejacz and Dębski, 2009).

Figure 5 Map of smoothed seismicity rates for Norway and Svalbard, based on the complete earthquake catalogues and regional completeness thresholds. Pink circles show grid point sources sized and coloured by normalised seismicity rate; blue circles show complete catalogue events used in the calculation. Figure created using ArcGIS. Background maps: ESRI.

359 3.1.6 Minimum magnitude

360 Data harvesting was limited to events with a magnitude of 1.0 and above. The minimum completeness magnitude
 361 for the continental dataset varied between magnitude 2.0, 2.5, and 3.0, depending on the region and the logic tree
 362 branch. For the Svalbard dataset, the minimum completeness magnitude was set to 3.0, 3.5, and 4.0. These values
 363 reflect regional detection thresholds, which varied with station coverage. See Fig. 4 for further details. For the hazard
 364 calculations, a minimum magnitude of 4.0 was adopted, as this represents the threshold at which damage may begin
 365 to occur Sargeant et al. (2008). This choice aligns with the minimum magnitude values used in the Swedish and UK
 366 national hazard models (Joshi et al., 2024; Mosca et al., 2022).

3.1.7 Maximum magnitude

Logic trees were implemented to define the maximum magnitude limits for the seismogenic source model (Fig. 6). For continental Norway, the logic tree consisted of four branches based on the reported maximum magnitude of 6.0, with additional increments of 0.3 and 0.6, each assigned a weight of 0.4. Two higher-magnitude branches were also included: one at 7.0 with a weight of 0.15, and another at 7.5 with a weight of 0.05. The lower-magnitude branches align with standard practice and carry the majority of the total weight. The higher-magnitude branches were incorporated to account for plausible but less likely scenarios, supported by geological evidence of an approximately 80 km fault scarp in Finnmark. This feature, with a fault displacement of 10 meters, and similar faults mapped in the region, could support magnitudes around 6.9 around 500-450 years ago (Mattila et al., 2019; Olsen and Olesen, 2023; Smith et al., 2021).

Although the major stress conditions have changed following deglaciation, the relatively short recording history and the unpredictable nature of seismicity in stable continental regions introduce significant uncertainty in hazard assessments (Johnston and Kanter, 1990). To account for this unpredictability and for the sake of completeness we chose not to disregard the potential for future large events, which is reflected in the two low-probability branches of the logic tree. While this inclusion enhances the representation of potential seismic sources, its impact on estimated hazard levels may be limited. A study by Fülöp et al. (2022) found that variations in M_{max} had only a minor effect on PGA values in low-seismicity regions.

For Svalbard we adopted a similar logic tree, see Fig. 6, consisting of four branches. Two primary branches were based on the reported maximum magnitude of 6.2, with values of 6.5 and 6.7, each assigned a weight of 0.35. As with continental Norway, two higher-magnitude branches were also included to account for the possibility of more severe events, given the relatively short seismic recording history in the region. These branches, set at magnitudes 7.0 and 7.5, were given weights of 0.25 and 0.05, respectively.

3.1.8 Full seismogenic source model logic tree

The full seismogenic logic trees generated 144 nodes for continental Norway and 72 nodes for Svalbard (Fig. 6). The weighting for variance in a and b values, at $1/6$, are tied to standard deviation. The seismogenic logic trees follow the same structure for both continental Norway and Svalbard, with additional branches for the magnitude-limited and time-limited catalogues added for continental Norway.

3.2 Ground Motion Model

There is currently no ground motion model available, developed specifically for Norway due to the generally low level of seismicity, the apparent absence of larger events in recent years, and the spatial distribution of events relative to the seismic network, nor was it feasible based on these challenges to develop a bespoke Ground Motion Model (GMM) for Norway (Bommer et al., 2010).

Instead, we adopted regional GMMs and models from tectonically similar regions, assigning weights to provide a reasonable approximation for Norwegian conditions. To assess the suitability of these models, we compared their predicted ground motion values with locally recorded ground motions from recent moderate-magnitude events. Using a tectonic zonation approach, we assigned the regional tectonic setting as shallow crustal in the coastal and

SEISMOGENIC SOURCE MODEL LOGIC TREE

GROUND MOTION MODEL LOGIC TREE

Figure 6 Full logic trees used in the seismic hazard assessment. **Upper:** Continental Norway seismogenic source model with four branches—three area zonation approaches and one smoothed seismicity model—each including uncertainty in maximum magnitude and ± 1 standard deviation for a - and b -values. **Middle:** Svalbard seismogenic source model with two branches: area zonation and smoothed seismicity, including similar parameter uncertainties. **Lower:** Ground motion model logic tree with two tectonic branches: shallow crustal (ESHM20, weight 1) and cratonic (ESHM20 Craton 0.4, FennoG16 0.4, crustal 0.2); only the shallow crustal branch applies to Svalbard. Branch weights are shown in blue.

403 offshore regions, as well as in the Caledonian mountain belt. In contrast, the Swedish and Finnish regions were
 404 classified as cratonic, following the outline of the Fennoscandian Shield. This classification is consistent with the
 405 Swedish national hazard model (Joshi et al., 2024) and the ESHM20 model (Danciu et al., 2021). Fig. 3 illustrates the
 406 tectonic zonation, with the cratonic region crosshatched in purple for enhanced visibility. For Svalbard, the entire
 407 region was classified as shallow crustal.

408 The models considered included the shallow crustal and stable craton branches of the ESHM20 scaled backbone
 409 GMM (Weatherill and Cotton, 2020; Weatherill et al., 2020), the Finnish adaptation of the Graizer 2016 model (Fülöp

et al., 2020; Graizer, 2016) was also considered for the cratonic region. These models were chosen based on tectonic regime, magnitude range and VS30 range. To validate the selected models, we collected ground motion data from seismometers located onshore in mainland Norway and on Svalbard. We investigated events occurring after the year 2000, with a moment magnitude (M_w) of 3.75 or greater for mainland Norway, and 4.5 or greater for Svalbard. This selection yielded 209 recordings from 36 events, each recorded at up to 17 stations, with an average of 4 records per event. Epicentral distances ranged from 61 km to 500 km. Most events were located offshore along the continental margin of Northern Norway, along the ridge southwest of the Svalbard archipelago, inner and outer parts of Storfjorden, with additional events in the central and northern North Sea, a M_w 4.1 event in Kattegat (2012), and a M_w 4.7 event in central Sweden (2014). Fig. 7 right shows the spatial distribution of events and recording stations. For each event, both horizontal components of ground motion were extracted, averaged, and plotted against epicentral distance. The observed ground motions were then compared with predictions from three GMMs: the ESHM20, ESHM20 Craton and FennoG16. Comparisons were made across three magnitude bins: [3.1–4.0], [4.1–5.0], and [5.1–6.0], as illustrated in Fig. 7 left.

Figure 7 Earthquakes and stations used for ground motion model validation (right) and comparison of recorded ground motions with selected models (left). The map shows events sized by magnitude and coloured by number of records, with green triangles marking stations used in validation. The scatter plot compares observed average horizontal accelerations versus epicentral distance for Svalbard and continental Norway events against predictions from ESHM20, ESHM20 Craton, and FennoG16. Map created using ArcGIS Pro, background map; ESRI.

Based on the observed fit to recorded ground motions and the applicable magnitude and distance ranges (see Table 3), we developed a Ground Motion Model (GMM) logic tree with two sections corresponding to distinct tectonic settings: a cratonic region in the east and a shallow crustal region in the west. Each tectonic branch is further sub-

426 divided into regional and local model components. For the shallow crustal region, we adopted the ESHM20 crustal
 427 model. Although other models were considered, using only the ESHM20 crustal model for the coastal regions allows
 428 for direct comparison with both the ESHM20 model and the Swedish national hazard model. We applied a mixed
 429 model approach, assigning a weight of 0.8 to cratonic models and 0.2 to crustal models, consistent with the original
 430 configuration of the cratonic branch in ESHM20, to account for possible tectonic transitions near the craton–crustal
 431 boundary. The cratonic component was represented by a combination of ESHM20 Craton and FennoG16, each as-
 432 signed a weight of 0.4, while the 0.2 weight was allocated to the ESHM20 crustal model. The complete ground motion
 433 logic tree is illustrated in Fig. 6, with branch weights indicated in blue. For the Svalbard hazard calculations, the GMM
 434 logic tree was limited to the shallow crustal branch only, reflecting the regional tectonic setting of the archipelago.

435 By combining validated regional and national models with appropriate weighting based on model fit and relative
 436 confidence, we achieve a reasonable approximation of expected ground shaking. This approach serves as a practical
 substitute for a bespoke model in regions with limited strong-motion data.

Model	Tectonic regime	Magnitude range	Vs30 range	Distance range
ESHM20 Crustal	Crustal	Mw 3–7.4	90–3000 m/s	0–545 km
ESHM20 Craton	Craton	Mw 3–7.4	90–3000 m/s	0–545 km
FennoG16	Craton	Mw 2–7	2800 m/s	0–300 km

Table 1 Ground motion model parameter overview

437

438 **3.3 Model parameters**

439 The hazard model was computed for two representative site conditions: a VS30 of 800 m/s, commonly used in engi-
 440 neering applications, and a VS30 of 3000 m/s, which better reflects hard rock conditions and allows for direct com-
 441 parison with ESHM20, as well as local and regional models. Calculations were performed on a uniform grid with a
 442 resolution of 10×10 km, covering the entire area of interest. The results were clipped to the national borders for pre-
 443 sentation and interpretation. The contour lines have been smoothed to limit noise. Hazard estimates were produced
 444 for two exceedance probabilities: a yearly rate of 0.002105, corresponding to a return period of 475 years (or a 10%
 445 probability of exceedance in 50 years), and a yearly rate of 0.0004, corresponding to a return period of 2500 years (or
 446 a 2% probability of exceedance in 50 years).

447 **4 Results**

448 In this section we present the hazard maps for Svalbard and continental Norway for a 475- and 2500-year return
 449 period. The maps presented here correspond to a VS30 of 3000 m/s. Equivalent maps were created for VS30 = 800
 450 m/s which are included in the online supplements. Most of Norway exhibits very hard rock conditions, and the
 451 model derived for 3000 m/s is thus considered more representative for some parts of the country. However, most
 452 building codes, such as Eurocode8 (Rønnquist et al., 2012), consider hazard values for VS30=800 m/s. Comparing the
 453 PGA values estimated for the two VS30 values shows that the regional distribution of hazard shows no discernible
 454 differences, but that the overall hazard level is slightly higher utilizing a VS30 of 800m/s, as expected considering site
 455 amplification (Baker et al., 2021). It should be noted that a full site-response analysis may be needed for engineering
 456 applications.

Figure 8 Seismic hazard maps showing peak ground acceleration (PGA) for 475-year and 2500-year return periods. Upper: Continental Norway ($V_{s30} = 800$ m/s), clipped to the national boundary with major cities marked. Lower: Svalbard, clipped to the archipelago boundary. Contour intervals are 0.01 g and 0.025 g; warmer colours indicate higher hazard. Maps created in ArcGIS with ESRI basemaps.

4.1 Seismic hazard map continental Norway

Fig 17 illustrates the estimated seismic hazard across continental Norway for return periods of 475 years and 2500 years. The areas of elevated hazard closely follow the spatial distribution of observed seismicity and historically significant events, and are near identical between the two return periods, with maxima slightly more constrained for 475-year than 2500-year return period. The scale was adjusted between the two maps in order to enhance the regional variance. The cities targeted for further analysis are highlighted with yellow squares.

The highest peak ground acceleration (PGA) levels are observed along the western coast of Norway, particularly between Bergen and Ålesund, where the estimated PGA reaches 0.06–0.07 g for a 475-year return period and 0.17–0.18 g for a 2500-year return period (Fig. 8). This elevated hazard zone extends southward along the coast toward Kristiansand, albeit with slightly lower PGA values. In Eastern Norway, the Oslo region exhibits slightly elevated hazard levels, with PGA values of 0.02 g and 0.07 g for the 475-year and 2500-year return periods, respectively. The increased hazard encompasses the Oslofjord and stretches eastward toward the Swedish border. In Northern Norway, the Nordland region shows moderate seismic hazard, with PGA values of 0.04 g (475-year) and 0.135 g (2500-year). This elevated hazard zone closely follows the coastline between 65°N and 68.5°N. Additionally, the model identifies a distinct hazard zone in southern Finnmark, near postglacial fault systems close to the borders with Finland and Sweden. Local maxima of 0.04 g (475-year) and 0.137 g (2500-year) are observed, covering large portions of Finnmarksvidda. The peak hazard levels in Finnmark are comparable to those estimated for Nordland.

4.2 Seismic hazard map Svalbard

The seismic hazard model for Svalbard, presented in Fig. 8, indicates generally higher PGA values compared to continental Norway. For a V_{s30} of 800 m/s, the model estimates maximum PGA values of approximately 0.2 g for a 475-year return period and 0.43 g for a 2500-year return period in the coastal regions surrounding Storfjorden, located in the southeast. This elevated hazard area encompasses most of Edgeøya and the southern tip of Spitsbergen. Along the western coast of Spitsbergen toward the Mid-Atlantic Ridge, the model shows a general elevation in hazard levels, with PGA values of approximately 0.075 g (475-year) and 0.15–0.2 g (2500-year). Local peaks in this region reach 0.1 g and 0.23 g for the 475-year and 2500-year return periods, respectively. In the northern part of the archipelago, elevated PGA values are observed on Nordaustlandet, with local maxima reaching 0.09 g (475-year) and 0.2 g (2500-year). Near Longyearbyen, the main local settlement, the model estimates PGA values around 0.04 g for a 475-year return period and 0.09 g for a 2500-year return period. These values are comparable to elevated hazard levels found in Nordland on the mainland and can be considered moderate compared to the rest of the archipelago.

Overall, the estimated hazard levels at Svalbard are significantly higher than those in continental Norway. The regional maximum PGA of 0.2 g at Svalbard is approximately three times higher than the maximum PGA estimate of 0.064 g along the western coast of continental Norway, and approximately five times higher than the elevated values of 0.04 g in Nordland and Finnmark.

4.3 Seismic hazard curves and disaggregation maps

To provide a more detailed perspective beyond the regional hazard maps, we also computed the mean and median hazard curves and disaggregation plots for sites of interest to better understand the factors influencing local hazard levels. Specifically, we computed results for seven Norwegian cities; Oslo, Bergen, Stavanger, Trondheim, Bodø, Tromsø, and Longyearbyen (Fig. 9) selected based on their relative population sizes and geographic distribution. The plots were created for a return period of 475 years and a vs30 of 800 m/s. The choice of vs30 had minimal impact on the produced results.

Overall, both the mean and median hazard curves indicate comparable probability levels across most cities. Notably, Trondheim exhibits consistently lower probability levels, while Longyearbyen shows elevated values at higher PGA levels. A comparison of the mean and median hazard curves within each city reveals similar trends, with the exception of Longyearbyen. Here, the mean hazard curve displays a significant increase in the probability of PGA values exceeding $10e-3g$, whereas the median curve maintains a more moderate probability across all PGA values. This discrepancy suggests that Longyearbyen's seismic hazard profile is more strongly influenced by low-probability, high-magnitude events, which disproportionately affect the mean hazard estimates.

Joint plot of hazard curves for Norwegian cities - 475 years, Vs30 = 800

Figure 9 Mean and median seismic hazard curves for seven cities across Norway; Oslo, Bergen, Stavanger, Trondheim, Bodø, Tromsø, and Longyearbyen. Calculated for a return period of 475 years and a vs30 of 800 m/s. Hazard curves calculated using OpenQuake. Plots created using Python.

To investigate potential contributing sources to these hazard curves we created disaggregation maps for the same cities, again using vs30 = 800 m/s and a return-period of 475 years. These plots (Fig. 10) illustrate the relative contributions to the estimated seismic hazard as a function of event magnitude and epicentral distance. Looking at these plots, we can identify potential driving mechanisms for the hazard, based on the location of the city and the regional distribution of seismicity.

The disaggregation map for Tromsø reveals a dispersed hazard profile, with contributions primarily from small and moderate magnitude events occurring at relatively close distances, predominantly within 50 km. A similar pat-

tern is observed in Trondheim, though with a slightly broader distribution extending up to 100 km. In contrast, Bodø exhibits a more concentrated hazard profile, dominated by small magnitude events located in close proximity (<50 km), fitting the local shallow clustering activity associated with Nordland. Bergen also shows a clear influence from nearby sources, with contribution from both smaller and more moderate magnitude events, likely reflecting offshore events. Stavanger is the only city to show notable contributions from distant (>200 km), high-magnitude events. This likely also reflects offshore seismicity in the Northern North Sea. The hazard profile for Oslo is evenly distributed across magnitudes, spread across shorter distances (<50km) for smaller events up to 100 km for moderate events, indicating a more diffuse hazard profile. Finally, Longyearbyen is characterized by dominant contributions from higher-magnitude events at short to moderate distances. This pattern is consistent with its mean hazard curve, supporting a low-probability, high-impact seismic scenario.

Although the ground motion model was validated using locally recorded data, most of the collected recordings were from greater distances, where model predictions showed good agreement. In contrast, at shorter distances, where model variability was more pronounced, we were only able to retrieve a limited number of data points due to the source-station geometry. The disaggregation analysis indicates the dominant contributions to hazard originate from nearby events (within 100 km). Unfortunately, this is precisely the range where ground motion recordings are sparse or entirely absent, which may impact our ability to assess model performance in the most critical distance range.

5 Discussion

The hazard maps presented in this paper are the result of extensive data validation, a newly developed smoothed seismicity model, a thorough completeness assessment and Fennoscandian collaboration on area zonation. Combined, these efforts aimed to produce a reliable hazard estimate designed to inform both engineering practices and societal preparedness. To assess the consistency and reliability of our hazard model, it is however imperative that we compare the predicted PGA values and spatial distribution of hazard with previous studies. In this section we will discuss choices and assumptions made and compare our results with previous hazard studies including ESHM20 (Danciu et al., 2021), the Swedish Joshi2023 hazard model (Joshi et al., 2024), the Norwegian Lindholm2025 model (Lindholm et al., 2025) and the Norwegian Bungum2000 model (Bungum et al., 2000).

Substantial effort was dedicated to the identification and removal of non-tectonic events from the earthquake catalogue. This was achieved by combining traditional time–magnitude filtering with density-based clustering algorithms to eliminate as many dependent events as possible. While effective for Norwegian regions—yielding b-values between 0.81 and 0.84—source zones in Sweden consistently showed higher b-values around 1.0. Comparison with the results from Joshi2023 confirmed this discrepancy, suggesting an overrepresentation of smaller events within Sweden in our catalogue, likely due to the inclusion of non-tectonic activity. To account for this, we adopted the a- and b-values from Joshi2023 for the corresponding area zones located in Sweden in our analysis. This improved the consistency of the hazard estimates for regions bordering Sweden. This does however mean that the model relies on external values, limiting the ability to directly verify or compare results with those presented in Joshi2023.

A collage of the hazard maps produced by the individual branches is provided in the online supplement (Fig.

Figure 10 Disaggregation maps highlighting the relative contribution to seismic hazard as a function of magnitude and epicentral distance for selected cities. Calculated using OpenQuake for 475-year return period and vs_{30} of 800 m/s. Bars are colour-coded by contribution level. The vertical axis shows relative contribution as percentage; the horizontal axis shows epicentral distance and magnitude. Plots created using python and assembled using Inkscape.

547 S11 and Fig. S12). The smoothed model results show a high sensitivity to variations in B-values. Using a fixed B-
 548 value of 0.8, representing a regional average, produced a similar hazard distribution to the zonation based model,
 549 but with lower peak levels. In Nordland, this approach slightly underestimated the hazard levels compared to area-
 550 zonation models. In Western Norway, the underestimation was even more pronounced, with peak hazard levels
 551 significantly lower than those indicated by the area models. Sensitivity analysis across a range of B-values revealed
 552 that peak hazard estimates are strongly influenced by the chosen B-value. Incorporating regionally varying B-values
 553 could improve accuracy, although this would reintroduce zonation bias. The lower peaks produced by the smoothed

554 models contribute to a reduction in overall hazard levels in the final model, but the modest weighting of 0.2 limits
555 their overall impact.

556 Our PGA values and their spatial distribution near the national border with Sweden are, as expected, consistent
557 with the Joshi2023 model. We obtain slightly higher PGA values near Oslo and slightly lower values in Finnmark.
558 However, the overall distribution of elevated PGA estimates remains broadly consistent across the two models. The
559 local elevation in hazard in the Finnmark region is likely driven by the more detailed monitoring of the post-glacial
560 faults by the Swedish National Seismic Network in northern Sweden (Lindblom et al., 2015; Lund et al., 2021), which
561 has enhanced detection capabilities and provided a more accurate depiction of the regional seismicity. The compar-
562 atively lower level in Finnmark may reflect choice of GMM, where our model introduces a crustal component to the
563 cratonic logic tree in line with the ESHM20 model, as opposed to the Swedish GMM which considers purely cratonic
564 branches.

565 The ESHM20 model shows elevated PGA values along the southwestern Norwegian coastline, which corresponds
566 well with our model. Both models also indicate a localized elevation in hazard in the Nordland region. The PGA
567 value estimates are comparable in the two models for both regions. However, ESHM20 does not capture the elevated
568 hazard levels observed in the Oslo region or in Finnmark, near the post-glacial faults. This could be attributed to
569 the higher minimum magnitude threshold of the ESHM20 catalogue, or to the coarser area zonation which could be
570 averaging local seismic clusters over a broader region.

571 When comparing our results to Lindholm2025, we observe a broadly similar regional distribution of the hazard.
572 Due to the low resolution and colour scale used in Lindholm2025, a direct value-to-value comparison is challeng-
573 ing. However, comparing the 0.02 g and 0.05 g contour lines, our closest approximation, we find that in western
574 Norway, the 0.02 g contour aligns well in the north, with a slight southward deviation with a broader extent towards
575 Kristiansand in our model. For the 0.05 g contour we see that our model estimates a more localised elevated hazard
576 area extending from Ålesund to Bergen, as opposed to Lindholm2025, which reaches even further south towards
577 Stavanger. Comparing the 0.02 g contour for the elevated PGA levels in the Oslo region we see a comparable extent
578 on the western edge, but that our contour also extends eastward toward Sweden, where we observe a maximum peak
579 at 0.03 g at the border. The regional maximum value of the Lindholm2025 model is somewhere between 0.02 g and
580 0.05 g, presumably located near Oslo. Notably, the influence of postglacial faults in southern Finnmark appears to
581 be absent in the Lindholm2025 model. This difference may be attributed to the Lindholm2025 catalogue or model
582 framework. A modest presence of earthquake activity is visible in both the zonation, and zonation-free seismicity
583 maps of the Lindholm2025 model; however, this modest seismic activity does not seem to significantly affect the final
584 hazard estimates. This seemingly limited impact may be due to the broad zonation applied by Lindholm2025 in the
585 region, which can obscure finer-scale variations, or it may result from the use of a highly segmented colour scale
586 combined with a wide value range, which reduces visual contrast and can lead to loss of detail in the representation
587 of subtle differences.

588 Until now, Lindholm2025 has been the only available seismic hazard map for Svalbard. In comparison, our re-
589 sults reveal overall lower PGA values. Both models indicate elevated hazard levels in Nordaustlandet, surrounding
590 Storfjorden region and toward the spreading ridge. The Lindholm2025 model presents a more spatially distributed

591 pattern of elevated PGA values across southern Spitsbergen, while our model has a more localised elevation along
592 the southern coastline. This discrepancy may be attributed to differences in zonation, as our model utilises a more
593 fine-grained model for Svalbard than Lindholm2025. The peak PGA value in Lindholm2025, in the coastal regions of
594 Storfjorden, likely exceeds that of our model: 0.2 g - 0.5 g in Lindholm2025 versus 0.2 g in our model, calculated for
595 a return period of 475 years and V_{s30} of 800 m/s.

596 The Bungum2000 model generally presents higher hazard values than more recent models. This discrepancy may
597 be attributed to the overall reduction in the number of moderate events in recent years, coinciding with the transition
598 to instrumental records. While the overall spatial distribution remains broadly consistent, the Bungum2000 model
599 shows elevated hazard levels extending further inland and covering more of the coastline compared to our results.
600 These differences may be due to the use of a smaller and more diffuse event catalogue, a difference in zonation, or
601 they may reflect better modelling capabilities and/or ground motion models in newer assessments.

602 Overall, the comparison demonstrates that our model aligns well with previously published hazard models in
603 terms of regional distribution and absolute PGA values, with the notable exception of the local increase in the hazard
604 estimate for the Finnmark region. This local elevation in hazard is likely not connected to maximum magnitude,
605 despite the link to the post-glacial faults and the associated theoretical maximum, as the maximum magnitude logic
606 tree is applied across the region to all area zones. The occurrence rates for the associated area zone are adopted
607 from the Swedish model, as the zone lies within Swedish national border, the estimated occurrence rates based on
608 our catalogue are slightly lower, potentially due to over-filtering of mining related activity in the region. Overview
609 plots for all area zones, including estimated and final occurrence rates are available in the supporting Jupyter Note-
610 book, linked in the online supplements. The zonation in the region is highly targeted and harmonised with Swedish
611 colleagues, separating the highly active area zone 25 Lapland Central from the more quiet area zones 10 Finnmark
612 and 11 Kola. The local elevation in hazard is thus likely a combination of targeted zonation and adoption of Swedish
613 occurrence rates. These Swedish occurrence rates are based on local expertise and targeted mapping of activity on
614 post-glacial faults, disentangling mining induced activity from tectonic events.

615 We consider our model a more robust estimate than the previously published ones, since it is based on a longer-
616 duration earthquake catalogue (despite its recent publication data, the Lindholm2025 model only considers earth-
617 quakes before 2018), which has gone through substantial cleaning and quality control. We utilize a zonation model
618 that has been harmonized across national borders in cooperation with experts from neighbouring countries com-
619 plemented with a smoothed zonation free model to capture local clusters and incorporate state-of-of-the-art ground
620 motion models which have been validated against the limited ground motion data available for our study area. On
621 top of this and arguably most importantly, our model is openly available and transparent for reproducibility and
622 usability.

623 **6 Conclusions**

624 This study presents updated seismic hazard models for Norway and Svalbard, developed for return periods of 475
625 and 2500 years, and for two site conditions characterized by V_{S30} values of 800 m/s and 3000 m/s.

626 The models are based on refined and comprehensive earthquake catalogues compiled from multiple national and

international sources. A harmonised area source zonation approach was employed, supplemented by a smoothed seismicity model to enhance robustness. The zonation model consisted of 31 area source zones for continental Norway and 18 area source zones for Svalbard. The final seismogenic source model logic tree comprises 144 branches for continental Norway and 72 for Svalbard, with weights assigned to reflect maximum magnitude estimates and catalogue completeness thresholds. To account for the region's varying tectonic settings, a geographically partitioned ground motion model logic tree was implemented, distinguishing between stable cratonic and shallow crustal domains. All calculations were performed using the OpenQuake engine (Pagani et al., 2014) following the workflow established in ESHM20 (Danciu et al., 2021).

We obtain the highest hazard levels in coastal regions of western Norway, in Nordland, southern Finnmark and in the Oslo region. The PGA for continental Norway, based on a 475-year return period and a reference site condition of $V_{s30} = 800$ m/s, reaches up to 0.06 g near the coast of western Norway. In addition to the national maximum in Western Norway we also see local peaks in southern Finnmark (0.04 g), Nordland (0.03 g), and Oslo region (0.03 g). Compared to previously published models, the regional distribution is more spatially constrained, generally predicting comparable or lower hazard levels across most areas, with the exception of Finnmark. For Svalbard, the greatest hazard is found in the coastal regions surrounding Storfjorden with a PGA of 0.15 g. Elevated values are also observed toward the ridge (0.1 g), at Edgeøya (0.075-0.15 g) and Nordaustlandet (0.05 g), all based on the same return period and site condition.

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Data and code availability

The earthquake catalogues and seismogenic source models were prepared using custom Python routines developed for this project and informed by existing Seisan routines and the Open Quake Hazard Modellers Toolkit. All maps are prepared using ArcGIS Pro with ESRI background maps. The earthquake catalogues, Jupyter notebooks, configuration files, produced figures and produced models are made available on Zenodo at time of publication. The earthquake catalogues are shared as csv files following the OpenQuake format, this includes separate catalogues for Svalbard, and for the three different completeness settings for continental Norway. The Jupyter notebooks are exported to html for convenience in terms of packages and supporting scripts. Hazard maps for each unique setting are also made available both in the online supplement and in the Zenodo data package.

661 **Competing interests**

662 No competing interests.

663 **References**

664 Baker, J. W., Bradley, B. A., and Stafford, P. J., 2021. Seismic hazard and risk analysis. Cambridge University Press.

665 Bommer, J. J., Douglas, J., Scherbaum, F., Cotton, F., Bungum, H., and Fah, D. On the Selection of Ground-Motion Prediction Equations for
666 Seismic Hazard Analysis. *Seismological Research Letters*, 81(5):783–793, Aug. 2010. doi: 10.1785/gssrl.81.5.783.

667 Bungum, H. and Dahle, A. *On the Determination of Seismic Hazards in Norwegian Continental Shelf Areas*, page 665–677. Springer Nether-
668 lands, 1989. doi: 10.1007/978-94-009-2311-9_37.

669 Bungum, H. and Lindholm, C. Seismo- and neotectonics in Finnmark, Kola and the southern Barents Sea, part 2: Seismological analysis
670 and seismotectonics. *Tectonophysics*, 270(1–2):15–28, Feb. 1997. doi: 10.1016/s0040-1951(96)00139-4.

671 Bungum, H., Mitchell, B., and Kristoffersen, Y. Concentrated earthquake zones in Svalbard. *Tectonophysics*, 82(3–4):175–188, Feb. 1982.
672 doi: 10.1016/0040-1951(82)90044-0.

673 Bungum, H., Alsaker, A., Kvamme, L. B., and Hansen, R. A. Seismicity and seismotectonics of Norway and nearby continental shelf areas.
674 *Journal of Geophysical Research: Solid Earth*, 96(B2):2249–2265, Feb. 1991. doi: 10.1029/90jb02010.

675 Bungum, H., Lindholm, C. D., Dahle, A., Woo, G., Nadim, F., Holme, J. K., Gudmestad, O. T., Hagberg, T., and Karthigeyan, K. New Seis-
676 mic Zoning Maps for Norway, the North Sea, and the United Kingdom. *Seismological Research Letters*, 71(6):687–697, Nov. 2000.
677 doi: 10.1785/gssrl.71.6.687.

678 Burton, P. W. and Marrow, P. C. *Seismic Hazard and Earthquake Source Parameters in the North Sea*, page 633–664. Springer Netherlands,
679 1989. doi: 10.1007/978-94-009-2311-9_36.

680 Byrkjeland, U., Bungum, H., and Eldholm, O. Seismotectonics of the Norwegian continental margin. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Solid*
681 *Earth*, 105(B3):6221–6236, Mar. 2000. doi: 10.1029/1999jb900275.

682 Chan, W. and Mitchell, B. Intraplate earthquakes in Northern Svalbard. *Tectonophysics*, 114(1–4):181–191, Apr. 1985. doi: 10.1016/0040-
683 1951(85)90012-5.

684 Cornell, C. A. et al. Engineering seismic risk analysis. *Bulletin of the seismological society of America*, 58(5):1583–1606, 1968.

685 Dahle, A. Scandinavian Earthquake Archive. online, 2025. https://nordquake.net/Scandinavian_earthquake_archive/Scandinavian_earthquake_archive.html. Accessed: 2025-11-19.
686

687 Danciu, L., Nandan, S., Reyes, C. G., Basili, R., Weatherill, G., Beauval, C., Rovida, A., Vilanova, S., Sesetyan, K., Bard, P.-Y., et al. The 2020
688 update of the European Seismic Hazard Model-ESHM20: model overview. *EFHR Technical Report*, 1, 2021.

689 *Large magnitude earthquakes of late Holocene age in the Precambrian of Finnmark, Northern Norway*, Mar. 2020. EGU General Assembly
690 2020, Copernicus GmbH. doi: 10.5194/egusphere-egu2020-21749.

691 *The Comparison of the 2020 European and the Finnish Seismic Hazard Models at Two Nuclear Power Plant Sites in Finland*, Jan. 2025. EGU
692 General Assembly 2024, Copernicus GmbH. doi: 10.5194/egusphere-egu24-15663.

693 Fejerskov, M. and Lindholm, C. Crustal stress in and around Norway: an evaluation of stress-generating mechanisms. *Geological Society,*
694 *London, Special Publications*, 167(1):451–467, Jan. 2000. doi: 10.1144/gsl.sp.2000.167.01.19.

695 Fjeldskaar, W., Lindholm, C., Dehls, J. F., and Fjeldskaar, I. Postglacial uplift, neotectonics and seismicity in Fennoscandia. *Quaternary*
696 *Science Reviews*, 19(14–15):1413–1422, Oct. 2000. doi: 10.1016/s0277-3791(00)00070-6.

- 697 Frankel, A. et al. Mapping seismic hazard in the central and eastern United States. *Seismological Research Letters*, 66(4):8–21, 1995.
- 698 Fülöp, L., Jussila, V., Aapasuo, R., Vuorinen, T., and Mäntyniemi, P. A Ground-Motion Prediction Equation for Fennoscandian Nuclear Instal-
699 lations. *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America*, 110(3):1211–1230, May 2020. doi: 10.1785/0120190230.
- 700 Fülöp, L., Mäntyniemi, P., Malm, M., Toro, G., Crespo, M. J., Schmitt, T., Burck, S., and Välikangas, P. Probabilistic seismic hazard anal-
701 ysis in low-seismicity regions: an investigation of sensitivity with a focus on Finland. *Natural Hazards*, 116(1):111–132, Oct. 2022.
702 doi: 10.1007/s11069-022-05666-4.
- 703 Fülöp, L., Karlsen, M. K., Sørensen, M., Voss, P., Mäntyniemi, P., and Lund, B. Harmonized inputs to PSHA: Seismic source zoning (SSZs) and
704 earthquake catalogues across Northern Europe–Progress in 2024. Technical report, NKS Secretariat, 2025.
- 705 Galloway, D. Bulletin of British earthquakes 2014. Technical report, British Geological Survey, 2016.
- 706 Gee, D. G. and Stephenson, R. A. The European lithosphere: an introduction. *Geological Society, London, Memoirs*, 32(1):1–9, Jan. 2006.
707 doi: 10.1144/gsl.mem.2006.032.01.01.
- 708 Gee, D. G. and Teben'kov, A. M. Svalbard: a fragment of the Laurentian margin. *Geological Society, London, Memoirs*, 30(1):191–206, Jan.
709 2004. doi: 10.1144/gsl.mem.2004.030.01.16.
- 710 GEUS Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland. Danish Seismological Network, 1976. doi: 10.7914/NW3X-DF02.
- 711 Graizer, V. Ground-Motion Prediction Equations for Central and Eastern North America. *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America*, 106
712 (4):1600–1612, June 2016. doi: 10.1785/0120150374.
- 713 Gregersen, S., Lindholm, C., Korja, A., Lund, B., Uski, M., Oinonen, K., Voss, P. H., and Keiding, M. *Seismicity and Sources of Stress in*
714 *Fennoscandia*, page 177–197. Cambridge University Press, Dec. 2021. doi: 10.1017/9781108779906.014.
- 715 Grunthal, G., Group, G. R. . W., et al. Seismic hazard assessment for central, north and northwest Europe: GSHAP Region 3, 1999.
- 716 Hansen, R. A., Bungum, H., and Alsaker, A. Three recent larger earthquakes offshore Norway. *Terra Nova*, 1(3):284–295, May 1989.
717 doi: 10.1111/j.1365-3121.1989.tb00371.x.
- 718 Havskov, J. and Bungum, H. Source parameters for earthquakes in the northern North Sea. *Norsk Geologisk Tidsskrift*, 67:51–58, 1987.
- 719 Havskov, J., Voss, P. H., and Ottemöller, L. Seismological Observatory Software: 30 Yr of SEISAN. *Seismological Research Letters*, 91(3):
720 1846–1852, Mar. 2020. doi: 10.1785/0220190313.
- 721 Jerkins, A. E., Oye, V., Alvizuri, C., Halpaap, F., and Kværna, T. The 21 March 2022 Mw 5.1 Tampen Spur Earthquake, North Sea: Location,
722 Moment Tensor, and Context. *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America*, 114(2):741–757, Nov. 2023. doi: 10.1785/0120230163.
- 723 Johnston, A. C. and Kanter, L. R. Earthquakes in stable continental crust, 1990.
- 724 Joshi, N., Lund, B., and Roberts, R. Probabilistic seismic hazard assessment of Sweden. *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences*, 24(11):
725 4199–4223, Nov. 2024. doi: 10.5194/nhess-24-4199-2024.
- 726 Junek, W. N., Roman-Nieves, J. I., and Woods, M. T. Tectonic implications of earthquake mechanisms in Svalbard. *Geophysical Journal*
727 *International*, 196(2):1152–1161, Dec. 2013. doi: 10.1093/gji/ggt448.
- 728 Lindblom, E., Lund, B., Tryggvason, A., Uski, M., Bödvarsson, R., Juhlin, C., and Roberts, R. Microearthquakes illuminate the deep structure
729 of the endglacial Pärvie fault, northern Sweden. *Geophysical Journal International*, 201(3):1704–1716, Apr. 2015. doi: 10.1093/gji/ggv112.
- 730 Lindholm, C., Bungum, H., Ghione, F., Meslem, A., Huang, C., and Oye, V. Earthquakes and seismic hazard for Norway and Svalbard. *Journal*
731 *of Seismology*, 29(1):107–126, Jan. 2025. doi: 10.1007/s10950-024-10270-z.
- 732 Lund, B., Schmidt, P., Hossein Shomali, Z., and Roth, M. The Modern Swedish National Seismic Network: Two Decades of Intraplate Micro-
733 seismic Observation. *Seismological Research Letters*, 92(3):1747–1758, Mar. 2021. doi: 10.1785/0220200435.

- 734 Mäntyniemi, P., Wahlström, R., Lindholm, C., and Kijko, A. Seismic hazard in Fennoscandia: A regionalized study. *Tectonophysics*, 227(1–4):
735 205–213, Nov. 1993. doi: 10.1016/0040-1951(93)90095-2.
- 736 Mäntyniemi, P., Kijko, A., and Retief, P. Parametric-historic procedure for seismic hazard assessment and its application to northern Europe.
737 *Bollettino di Geofisica Teorica ed Applicata*, 42(1-2):41–55, 2001.
- 738 Mäntyniemi, P., Sørensen, M. B., and Tatevossian, R. E. Testing the Environmental Seismic Intensity Scale on Data Derived from the
739 Earthquakes of 1626, 1759, 1819, and 1904 in Fennoscandia, Northern Europe. *Geosciences*, 11(1):14, Dec. 2020. doi: 10.3390/geo-
740 sciences11010014.
- 741 Mattila, J., Ojala, A., Ruskeenieni, T., Palmu, J.-P., Aaltonen, I., Käpyaho, A., Lindberg, A., and Sutinen, R. Evidence of multiple slip events on
742 postglacial faults in northern Fennoscandia. *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 215:242–252, July 2019. doi: 10.1016/j.quascirev.2019.05.022.
- 743 McGuire, R. K. Computations of seismic hazard. *Annals of Geophysics*, 36(3–4), Nov. 1993. doi: 10.4401/ag-4263.
- 744 Meier, M., Schlindwein, V., Scholz, J., Geils, J., Schmidt-Aursch, M. C., Krüger, F., Czuba, W., and Janik, T. Segment-Scale Seismicity of the
745 Ultraslow Spreading Knipovich Ridge. *Geochemistry, Geophysics, Geosystems*, 22(2), Feb. 2021. doi: 10.1029/2020gc009375.
- 746 Mitchell, B. J. and Chan, W.-W. Characteristics of earthquakes in the Heerland seismic zone of eastern Spitsbergen. *Polarforschung*, 48(1/2):
747 31–40, 1978.
- 748 Mitchell, B. J., Bungum, H., Chan, W. W., and Mitchell, P. B. Seismicity and present-day tectonics of the Svalbard region. *Geophysical Journal*
749 *International*, 102(1):139–149, July 1990. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-246x.1990.tb00536.x.
- 750 Morozov, A. N., Vaganova, N. V., and Konechnaya, Y. V. The October 14, 1908 MW 6.6 earthquake in the Barents and Kara sea region of the
751 Arctic: Relocation based on instrumental data. *Polar Science*, 20:160–166, June 2019. doi: 10.1016/j.polar.2019.05.001.
- 752 Mosca, I., Sargeant, S., Baptie, B., Musson, R. M. W., and Pharaoh, T. C. The 2020 national seismic hazard model for the United Kingdom.
753 *Bulletin of Earthquake Engineering*, 20(2):633–675, Jan. 2022. doi: 10.1007/s10518-021-01281-z.
- 754 Mosca, I., Baptie, B., Haslam, R., Gafeira, J., and Jenkins, G. Seismic hazard assessment for the UK offshore Exclusive Economic Zone.
755 Technical report, British Geological Survey, 2024.
- 756 Oinonen, K., Uski, M., Soosalu, H., and Lund, B. A joint Fennoscandian earthquake catalogue FENCAT, version FENCAT17, 2024.
757 doi: 10.23729/8FE15AB2-E805-447C-934E-21CB0463414B.
- 758 Olesen, O., Bungum, H., Dehls, J., Lindholm, C., Pascal, C., and Roberts, D. Neotectonics, seismicity and contemporary stress field in
759 Norway—mechanisms and implications. *Quaternary Geology of Norway, Geological Survey of Norway Special Publication*, 13:145–174,
760 2013.
- 761 Olsen, L. and Olesen, O. Trenching and 14C dating of the postglacial Stuoragurra Fault Complex in Finnmark, Northern Norway, and geo-
762 hazard implications. Technical report, Norges geologiske undersøkelse, 2023. [https://openarchive.ngu.no/ngu-xmlui/handle/11250/
763 3133534](https://openarchive.ngu.no/ngu-xmlui/handle/11250/3133534).
- 764 Ottemöller, L., Storheim, B. M., Atakan, K., Havskov, J., and Sørensen, M. B. Norwegian National Seismic Network Decade report 2001-2010.
765 *Sci. Rep.*, 2013.
- 766 Ottemöller, L., Strømme, M. L., and Storheim, B. M. Seismic Monitoring and Data Processing at the Norwegian National Seismic Network.
767 *Summary of the Bulletin of the International Seismological Centre*, 52(1):27–40, July 2018. doi: 10.31905/1m97csyl.
- 768 Ottemöller, L., Kim, W.-Y., Waldhauser, F., Tjåland, N., and Dallmann, W. The Storfjorden, Svalbard, Earthquake Sequence
769 2008–2020: Transtensional Tectonics in an Arctic Intraplate Region. *Seismological Research Letters*, 92(5):2838–2849, May 2021.
770 doi: 10.1785/0220210022.
- 771 Pagani, M., Monelli, D., Weatherill, G., Danciu, L., Crowley, H., Silva, V., Henshaw, P., Butler, L., Nastasi, M., Panzeri, L., Simionato, M., and

- 772 Vigano, D. OpenQuake Engine: An Open Hazard (and Risk) Software for the Global Earthquake Model. *Seismological Research Letters*, 85
773 (3):692–702, May 2014. doi: 10.1785/0220130087.
- 774 Pirlı, M., Schweitzer, J., Ottemoller, L., Raeesi, M., Mjelde, R., Atakan, K., Guterch, A., Gibbons, S. J., Paulsen, B., Debski, W., Wiejacz, P., and
775 Kvaerna, T. Preliminary Analysis of the 21 February 2008 Svalbard (Norway) Seismic Sequence. *Seismological Research Letters*, 81(1):
776 63–75, Jan. 2010. doi: 10.1785/gssrl.81.1.63.
- 777 Rønquist, A., Remseth, S., and Lindholm, C. Earthquake engineering design practice in Norway: Implementation of Eurocode 8. In *The*
778 *15th World Conference on Earthquake Engineering, Lisbon, Portugal, 2012*.
- 779 Sargeant, S. L., Stafford, P. J., Lawley, R., Weatherill, G., Weston, A.-J. S., Bommer, J. J., Burton, P. W., Free, M., Musson, R. M. W., Kuuyuur,
780 T., and Rossetto, T. Observations from the Folkestone, U.K., Earthquake of 28 April 2007. *Seismological Research Letters*, 79(5):672–687,
781 Sept. 2008. doi: 10.1785/gssrl.79.5.672.
- 782 Shiddiqi, H. A., Ottemöller, L., Rondenay, S., Halpaap, F., Gradmann, S., and Michálek, J. Crustal structure and intraplate seismic-
783 ity in Nordland, Northern Norway: insight from seismic tomography. *Geophysical Journal International*, 230(2):813–830, Feb. 2022.
784 doi: 10.1093/gji/ggac086.
- 785 Smith, C. A., Mikko, H., and Grigull, S. *Glacially Induced Faults in Sweden: The Rise and Reassessment of the Single-Rupture Hypothesis*, page
786 218–230. Cambridge University Press, Dec. 2021. doi: 10.1017/9781108779906.016.
- 787 Sørensen, M. B., Havskov, J., Storheim, B. M., Ottemöller, L., and Atakan, K. Jordskjelvstasjonen i Bergen gjennom 125 år. *Norwegian*
788 *Journal of Geology*, June 2024. doi: 10.17850/njgsp2-2.
- 789 The Norwegian Directorate for Civil Protection(DSB). Analyser av krisescenarioer 2019. [https://www.dsb.no/siteassets/rapporter-og-](https://www.dsb.no/siteassets/rapporter-og-publikasjoner/rapporter/analyser-av-krisescenarioer-2019.pdf#page=107.38)
790 [publikasjoner/rapporter/analyser-av-krisescenarioer-2019.pdf#page=107.38](https://www.dsb.no/siteassets/rapporter-og-publikasjoner/rapporter/analyser-av-krisescenarioer-2019.pdf#page=107.38), 2019. Accessed: 2025-11-19.
- 791 Uski, M., Oinonen, K., Lund, B., Soosalu, H., Ottemöller, L., Sørensen, M. B., Voss, P. H., and Korja, A. FENCAT—an update of the Fennoscandian
792 earthquake catalogue. *Geophysical Journal International*, 242(3), June 2025. doi: 10.1093/gji/ggaf242.
- 793 Voss, P., Larsen, T. B., and Dahl-Jensen, T. Earthquake Hazard in Denmark, 2015. doi: 10.22008/GPUB/30674.
- 794 Wahlstrom, R. and Grunthal, G. Probabilistic Seismic Hazard Assessment (Horizontal PGA) for Fennoscandia Using the Logic Tree Approach
795 for Regionalization and Nonregionalization Models. *Seismological Research Letters*, 72(1):33–45, Jan. 2001. doi: 10.1785/gssrl.72.1.33.
- 796 Weatherill, G. and Cotton, F. A ground motion logic tree for seismic hazard analysis in the stable cratonic region of Europe: regionalisation,
797 model selection and development of a scaled backbone approach. *Bulletin of Earthquake Engineering*, 18(14):6119–6148, Aug. 2020.
798 doi: 10.1007/s10518-020-00940-x.
- 799 Weatherill, G., Pagani, M., and Garcia, J. Exploring earthquake databases for the creation of magnitude-homogeneous catalogues: tools for
800 application on a regional and global scale. *Geophysical Journal International*, 206(3):1652–1676, June 2016. doi: 10.1093/gji/ggw232.
- 801 Weatherill, G., Kotha, S. R., and Cotton, F. A regionally-adaptable “scaled backbone” ground motion logic tree for shallow seismicity in
802 Europe: application to the 2020 European seismic hazard model. *Bulletin of Earthquake Engineering*, 18(11):5087–5117, July 2020.
803 doi: 10.1007/s10518-020-00899-9.
- 804 Weichert, D. H. Estimation of the earthquake recurrence parameters for unequal observation periods for different magnitudes. *Bulletin of*
805 *the Seismological Society of America*, 70(4):1337–1346, Aug. 1980. doi: 10.1785/bssa0700041337.
- 806 Wiejacz, P. and Dębski, W. Podhale, Poland, earthquake of November 30, 2004. *Acta Geophysica*, 57(2):346–366, Mar. 2009.
807 doi: 10.2478/s11600-009-0007-8.
- 808 Woessner, J., Laurentiu, D., Giardini, D., Crowley, H., Cotton, F., Grünthal, G., Valensise, G., Arvidsson, R., Basili, R., Demircioglu, M. B.,
809 Hiemer, S., Meletti, C., Musson, R. W., Rovida, A. N., Sesetyan, K., and Stucchi, M. The 2013 European Seismic Hazard Model: key compo-

810 nents and results. *Bulletin of Earthquake Engineering*, 13(12):3553–3596, July 2015. doi: 10.1007/s10518-015-9795-1.

811 WOOD, R. M. The Scandinavian Earthquakes of 22 December 1759 and 31 August 1819. *Disasters*, 12(3):223–236, Sept. 1988.

812 doi: 10.1111/j.1467-7717.1988.tb00672.x.